

Perceptions of Department of Education Teachers on the Impact of Classroom Design on Student Engagement

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Abstract. The study explored the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of DepEd teachers about the impact of classroom design on student engagement following the DepEd's implementation of DepEd Order No. 21. The study revealed that the removal of classroom design resulted to hampered creativity, restricted engagement, and lack of consideration to learners' diversity. Teachers felt like they were being limited by the guidelines. The participants have also cited that the removal of classroom design restricted opportunities for students to learn as learning materials that could be posted in the classroom were removed. In order to cope, the teachers used the following strategies: creating a warm learning atmosphere, using of supplementary materials in teaching, and involving learners more through activities. The teachers emphasized the importance of creating a positive learning environment in which the connection between the teacher and learners could suffice for the lack of more learning resources. The usage of additional materials was also highlighted. Moreover, the insights gained were – classroom design helps in creating a positive classroom culture, communication plays a crucial role in the learning process, and there should be teacher involvement in the decision-making process. This way, students can benefit more from the learning process.

KEY WORDS

1. classroom design
2. student engagement
3. teaching and learning process
4. classroom culture

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1. Introduction

There is an increased interest in analyzing the effects of classroom design as educators and researchers look for new ways to improve student learning outcomes and academic engagement. In order to achieve the sustainable development goal for quality education, UNESCO (2018a) underscored the significance of developing educational facilities that are gender, child, and disability-sensitive. Given that children spend a large portion of their formative years in school, it is essential to give them a relaxing, safe, and enjoyable setting (Rokhshid, 2012). The physical learning environment, which includes elements like seating arrangements, lighting, color schemes, and technological integration, has the ability to have a major impact on students' cognitive functions, motivation, and overall learning experiences. While a growing corpus of research highlights the importance of classroom layout, a closer look at teachers' perceptions and experiences is necessary to grasp its practical consequences. In

the United States, Fisher et al. (2014) looked at the impact of classroom decorations on the ability of children to concentrate during instruction and retain lesson material. According to their research, classrooms with more decorations caused greater distractions, more off-task behavior, and worse learning gains than classrooms with fewer decorations. This implies that too much visual information can overwhelm a child's brain and prevent them from learning. The topic of whether children become accustomed to the visual surroundings with repeated exposure remains unanswered because earlier study concentrated on brief exposure to classroom decoration elements. This was the grounding in Montessori classrooms which prioritize visually uncluttered environments purporting that academic-related visual displays may not always be relevant to ongoing instruction potentially serving as visual distractions (Randolph et al., 2023). However, in a later study conducted by the same team of Fisher (2014), they hypothesized that even though lengthy exposure to a static visual environment led to partial habituation effects, the environment remained a substantial contributor to off-task behavior even after two weeks of exposure. In contrast, Barrett et al. (2013) in the United Kingdom looked at the connection between several environmental factors and student achievement in elementary school pupils. Even after taking socioeconomic status into account, they discovered that a number of school and classroom-level characteristics were related to children's success scores. Curiously, they found that accomplishment scores were adversely connected with classroom color ratings, debunking the notion that adding more color to the classroom encourages learning. This was corroborated by the study of Liu et al. (2022), which showed that warm colors like yellow and red improved concentration and learning performance while cool colors like blue and green encouraged relaxation and pleasure. Additional studies that emphasize

the advantages of light-colored rooms with a featured wall for optimal learning stimulation reinforce the fact that classrooms with white walls earned the lowest subjective regard (Barrett et al., 2015; Llinares et al., 2021). In the Philippines, Aquino's (2019) research found that classroom design, as a critical part of the learning environment, had a considerable impact on student academic achievement and engagement. As a result, the government and school administration should invest in enhancing classroom circumstances by providing adequate facilities to establish a welcoming and conducive learning environment. This was backed up by a local study undertaken by Björklund and Bramfors (2016), which highlighted the issue of insufficient space in Philippine schools resulted in overcrowded classrooms and little flexibility. Considering the realities on classroom design and its impact on learners, the Department of Education issued this month DepEd Order 21, series of 2023, known as the 2023 Brigada Eskwela Implementing Rules and Guidelines. Section B.2 of this order, which mandates that classroom walls remain bare without posters, decorations, or materials, sparked strong reactions. Further, teachers gave birth to "Operation Baklas" on social media, with both supporters and critics expressing their opinions. Education experts in the country such as Bahrami-Hessari have urged the education department to put teachers in charge of determining the optimum learning environment for their students (Cruz, 2023). She underlined that a lack of adequate materials in the classroom may impede the teaching and learning process. Likewise, in the same article Tuazon repeated these issues, emphasizing the inflexibility of the bare walls guideline, which fails to account individual pupils' developmental requirements. While some students thrive in any situation, the majority of learners benefit from a specific sort of learning environment. Teachers play a crucial role in the educational process, and their

experiences and insights offer valuable perspectives on how classroom design influences student engagement. This research aims to delve into educators' experiences and perspectives, shedding light on the intricate relationship between classroom design and student engagement. By exploring this connection from the teachers' viewpoint, we can gain a deeper understanding of how various design elements impact the learning environment and subsequently influence student motivation, participation, and overall academic achievement. The findings of this research will have the potential to inform evidence-based recommendations for educators, school administrators, and all other stakeholders involved in education planning.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study intends to provide insight into various challenges faced by public school teachers in relation to the impact of classroom design on student engagement, as well as the coping methods they employ given the scenario. The outcomes of the study would add to the body of knowledge available to better understand the new directions in the classroom learning environment in the basic education landscape of the Philippines.

1.2. Research Questions—This study aims to look into the experiences of public-school elementary teachers in the Department of Education on the impact of classroom design on student engagement.

- (1) What are the experiences of teachers on the impact of classroom design on student engagement?
- (2) What coping mechanisms did teachers use to counter challenges involving classroom design and student engagement?
- (3) What insights can be drawn from the findings of this study?

1.3. Significance of the Study—This study answers that burning call for understanding whether or how classroom design impacts a student's engagement, a pursuit inspired by the ideas of DepEd policies with regards to teaching in classrooms. As classroom environments directly affect students' academic engagement and behavior, the results of this study are crucial in terms of the impact of the recent "bare walls" directive under DepEd Order No. 21, Series of 2023. This policy requires the removal of decorative and instructional materials from classroom walls, aiming to standardize learning spaces but may be overlooking the different needs of students and the instructional strategies of teachers.

The importance of this research lies in its potential contribution to policy refinement and the development of evidence-based guidelines that will emphasize both teacher agency and student engagement. This research will clarify the role that classroom aesthetics and design can play in fostering or inhibiting effective learning environments through examination of how teachers adjust to the constraints and which coping mechanisms they use. These findings can assist educational administrators, policymakers, and teachers in developing adaptive classroom strategies that respect standardized policies but allow for the diverse learning preferences and cultural backgrounds of students. This study contributes to the broader discourse on sustainable and inclusive educational practices, as it highlights the importance of teacher input in educational reforms affecting the physical learning environment.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—

This study draws on two key theories: Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Learning (1987) and Richard Ryan and Edward Deci's (1985) Causality Orientations Theory. These theories provide a good foundation for comprehending the connection between classroom design and student involvement. Vygotsky's theory emphasizes the social and cultural components of learning, highlighting how people gain information through interactions with others and the cultural environment. This concept is important because it extends to classroom design, suggesting that it can either assist or block the sociocultural processes that are essential for student involvement. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) idea of Vygotsky, which depicts the gap between what a learner can perform independently and with assistance, is crucial. This notion emphasizes the construction of conditions that foster collaborative learning and peer relationships in the classroom. In the classroom, creating collaboration zones or group work areas can assist students scaffold one other's learning, making difficult activities more accessible and enjoyable. Furthermore, Vygotsky's theory adds the concept of scaffolding, in which learners receive temporary support with activities that are beyond their existing ability. Scaffolding can be made easier in the classroom by combining interactive displays, accessible materials, and instructional technologies. These design components serve as cognitive scaffolds, providing students with assistance and feedback, resulting in increased engagement and comprehension. Another important feature of Vygotsky's approach is cultural inclusion. By developing inclusive environments with culturally representative displays and resources, classroom design should take into account students' different cultural origins. Students gain a sense of belonging and involvement as a result of this. In addition, the Vygotskian viewpoint emphasizes the significance of social contact and teamwork in learning. Seating arrangements that foster face-to-face chats and collaborative workstations can help facilitate these connections in the classroom. A sense of community and involvement is fostered by comfortable and inviting spaces that encourage student discourse. When technology is intended for collaboration, it can also improve social ties and engagement. On the other hand, Richard Ryan and Edward Deci's Causality Orientations Theory investigates individuals' motivations and distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Students' causality orientations can be influenced by classroom design, which in turn affects their participation. Aesthetically pleasant decor, comfortable seating, and interesting resources can help to develop a design that promotes intrinsic motivation, where learning is enjoyable for its own purpose. Extrinsic motivation, which is driven by external rewards, on the other hand, may stifle real desire in learning. As a result, fostering an environment that values intrinsic drive might result in more passionate and willing student participation.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology used in this study which comprises the philosophical assumption, qualitative assumption, research design, research participants, role of the researcher, data gathering, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study and ethical considerations.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Researchers, often unconsciously, carry certain beliefs and philosophical underpinnings into their studies, influencing their approach to research questions and data collection. These beliefs are cultivated through academic train-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ing, mentorship, and participation in scholarly communities. Identifying and consciously deciding whether to incorporate these assumptions into the study is a critical challenge (Maxwell, 2005; Creswell, 2013). Creswell (2014) highlights the significance of understanding the philosophical presuppositions driving qualitative research. These presuppositions shape problem formulation, research questions, and data-gathering strategies. They are rooted in the researcher’s training and are reinforced by the scholarly community within which they operate. Additionally, awareness of the reviewers’ positions on key epistemological issues can be beneficial when making these philosophical assumptions about the research. In qualitative research, paradigms encompass philosophical presuppositions and beliefs spanning ontology, epistemology, axiology, and methodology (Creswell, 2014). Ontology addresses conceptions of reality, where qualitative researchers acknowledge the existence of multiple realities, which both participants and researchers embrace. Qualitative research aims to report these

diverse realities through various forms of evidence, often utilizing participants’ actual words and different perspectives. The epistemological foundation in qualitative research emphasizes the establishment of a personal connection between researchers and participants. Researchers compile subjective evidence based on individual viewpoints, facilitating knowledge discovery. The context in which participants live and work becomes crucial for understanding their perspectives and reducing subjectivity and distance between the researcher and study subjects (Guba Lincoln, 1988, as cited in Creswell, 2014). Lastly, axiological assumptions pertain to the values researchers bring into the study, which are explicitly disclosed in qualitative research. Researchers actively acknowledge their personal beliefs, biases, and the value-laden nature of the data collected during the study. This transparency extends to the acknowledgment of the value-laden character of the research itself (Guba Lincoln, 1994, as cited in Creswell, 2014).

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—

Individuals are inherently motivated to comprehend and develop their own interpretations of reality, based on their own unique personal experiences. In this setting, social constructivism provides a useful framework for qualitative research assumptions. It acknowledges that these meanings are diverse and nuanced rather than inherent or universal. According to social constructivism, researchers understand the need of examining the complexities of viewpoints rather than condensing them into a few preconceived

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study will employ a qualitative inquiry approach, specifically adopting a phenomenological design, to achieve its research objectives. Phenomenology, falling under the qualitative research paradigm, serves as a valuable method for researchers to gain insights from individuals' lived experiences (Creswell, 2013). The primary aim of the phenomenological research methodology is to delve into and grasp the genuine experiences of people. Instead of delving into causal relationships or making future predictions, it aims to describe and analyze the core of human experiences. Phenomenological research seeks to fathom the significance and essence of these lived experiences through in-depth interviews and a thorough examination of the collected data. This research process encompasses several key stages, including the selection of suitable participants, data collection through open-ended interviews, transcription and meticulous data analysis, culminating in the interpretation of the findings (Manen, 2014). In the course of a phenomenological investigation, researchers carefully select individuals

2.4. Research Participants—The study will employ purposive sampling technique which will include 10 participants from an ele-

mentary school in DepEd Region XI – Davao City Division. Purposive sampling is a non-probabilistic sampling strategy used in quali-

notions or categories. Furthermore, researchers place a high value on evaluating and assimilating participants' perspectives, recognizing that subjective interpretations are frequently deeply ingrained in historical and social settings. In essence, these meanings evolve as a result of interactions with others and are influenced by cultural and historical conventions that influence people's lives rather than being imposed on them. (Guba Lincoln, 1994).

who have encountered specific experiences and possess the ability to articulate and elucidate these experiences. Researchers engage in extensive interviews with participants, employing open-ended questions to encourage detailed and profound accounts of their experiences. Throughout these interviews, researchers diligently record participants' verbatim responses, paying attention not only to their words but also their tone, gestures, and facial expressions. Data analysis in phenomenological research involves identifying recurring themes and patterns within the collected data. Researchers meticulously examine the interview transcripts multiple times, seeking commonalities and shared elements within participants' accounts. These identified themes ultimately encapsulate the essence of the experiences under scrutiny. Researchers then analyze the results and compile a comprehensive report that includes a summary of the phenomena, its core ideas, and the prominent themes derived from the data analysis. Furthermore, the study delves into the implications of the findings and provides recommendations for potential future research endeavors (Moustakas, 1994).

mentary school in DepEd Region XI – Davao City Division. Purposive sampling is a non-probabilistic sampling strategy used in quali-

tative research to actively select specific individuals or instances based on their relevance to the research objectives and qualities that correspond with the study's focus. This strategy is distinguished by the researcher's deliberate and meticulous selection of participants or cases with the desired characteristics or experiences that can give useful insights to the research (Palinkas et al., 2015). Purposive sampling, as opposed to random sampling, relies on the researcher's judgment and skill in selecting informants or instances that will best suit the study goals, making it a planned and targeted method for qualitative investigations. For teachers to

be marked as participants, they have to satisfy the inclusion parameters set: (1) regular DepEd teachers whose assignment are in the specified elementary schools in the Davao City Division, (2) teachers who have teaching loads in the elementary schools; and (3) classroom advisers involved in classroom preparation during the Brigada Eskwela. Consequently, the exclusion criteria are as follows: (1) non-teaching personnel such as head teachers and administrative officers/assistants; (2) private elementary school teachers; (3) non-advisers who are not assigned to a classroom.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Given the inherent depth of qualitative research, ethical considerations take on paramount importance. Conducting face-to-face interviews with participants introduces significant ethical considerations that demand careful attention. Consent must be obtained willingly, with participants fully comprehending the nature of their involvement. Furthermore, participants must possess the capacity to provide informed consent. To uphold these principles, study participants will receive comprehensive information enabling them to make an informed decision about their continued participation in the research. Moreover, they will be afforded the freedom to decline participation if they so choose. Safeguarding participants' privacy involves refraining from disclosing their identities or any identifying information throughout the data col-

lection, analysis, and interpretation phases (Sutton Austin, 2015). Additionally, the researcher will take meticulous precautions to align the study with ethical guidelines governing qualitative research. Ensuring participants' comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives and procedures will be of paramount importance. Furthermore, the ethics committee at the Rizal Memorial Colleges Graduate School, comprising experts responsible for reviewing and approving research processes, has mandated the submission of requisite documentation to further ensure ethical compliance. These steps underscore the researcher's commitment to upholding ethical standards and safeguarding the rights and well-being of study participants (Kaiser, 2009). Ethical considerations remain fundamental in conducting qualitative research, particularly when it involves in-depth interactions with participants.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The function of the researcher in qualitative research is multifaceted and dynamic. The researcher is the primary instrument for data collection and interpretation, actively engaging with participants to understand their perspectives and experiences.

This involvement frequently demands empathy, reflexivity, and a thorough awareness of the study situation. According to Silverman (1997), the researcher's function extends beyond that of a passive observer; they actively generate meaning, shape the study process, and manage

the intricacies of ethical considerations. Researchers must maintain transparency and rigor throughout the study, acknowledging their influ-

2.7. *Data Collection*—The data gathering phase will follow the necessary steps to achieve a successful result generation. First, the researcher will develop an interview guide consisting of three key questions aimed at exploring the experiences of elementary public-school teachers regarding the impact of classroom design on student engagement. This step will involve a thorough consideration of teachers' challenges to uncover the root causes of these difficulties. Subsequently, experts will evaluate the interview guide, ensuring its quality. Ethical protocols will be diligently observed and applied during data collection. Permission to conduct the study will be sought through formal letters sent to various educational authorities, including the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, district supervisors, and school principals. Upon obtaining approval, the study will adhere to the conditions set by the authorized bodies. The interview sessions will be conducted in public settings with private areas to safeguard participants' confidentiality. All interviews will be audio recorded with partici-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—To ensure that the qualitative data are ushered to appropriate treatment, thematic analysis will be considered. This widely employed method is particularly effective when scrutinizing subjective data, often found in extensive textual materials such as interview transcripts. During this process, the researcher conducts a meticulous examination of the data to discern recurrent themes, ideas, and consistent patterns of meaning. When examining interview data, the primary objective is to identify and elucidate these themes, thus reveal-

ence on data collection and analysis while trying for impartiality and authenticity in expressing the participants' perspectives and experiences.

pants' consent. Moreover, participants will be instructed not to disclose individuals or locations by their names during the interviews. The researcher will provide a comprehensive explanation of the study's objectives, interview format, and the nature, benefits, and potential risks of participation to each participant. They will be informed that participation is voluntary and that strict confidentiality measures will apply to all gathered information. While remuneration will not be offered, participants will be made aware that their involvement could contribute to a better understanding of the phenomenon being investigated. Following the interviews, the data will be transcribed. It will be carefully streamlined before being presented back to the participants for validation. Participants will be given the opportunity to critically assess and provide feedback on the findings, which they will unanimously approve as an accurate representation of their thoughts, feelings, and experiences. Their validation will significantly enhance the credibility of the study. Subsequently, the gathered information from the IDIs will be organized into thematic categories for analysis.

ing the underlying patterns. An advantageous feature of thematic analysis is its adaptability, making it suitable for both deductive studies where the researcher has predefined interests and exploratory studies where the researcher embarks without preconceived notions of the sought-after patterns. Kaiser (2009) stressed that regardless of the nature or purpose of the study, the researcher's utmost commitment is to handle the data with care and precision, ensuring an accurate portrayal of the interview's findings.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The study’s framework is based on the Sociocultural Theory of Learning by Lev Vygotsky and the Causality Orientations Theory by Richard Ryan and Edward Deci, which provide a dual lens to understand how classroom environments influence teacher-student interactions and engagement.

Sociocultural Theory of Learning by Vygotsky (1987): This theory gives emphasis to the role of social interaction and cultural context in learning, which assumes that students learn through cooperative and supportive engagements within their environment. In this context, Vygotsky’s Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) becomes particularly relevant because it points out the importance of environments that encourage peer interaction and scaffolded support. This study analyzes classroom design elements as facilitators or inhibitors of social learning processes, specifically looking at how the absence of visual and instructional aids on walls affects opportunities for collaborative engagement.

Causality Orientations Theory (Ryan and Deci, 1985): Differentiates intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and studies how the immediate

environment affects people’s engagement and motivation.

The intrinsic motivation of the students is supposed to be enhanced by aesthetically pleasing and interactive classroom environments because they learn for personal satisfaction rather than due to external rewards. In this context, the paper questions whether the “bare walls” policy affects the motivation of the students since it provides a less stimulating environment visually, which would result in shifting from intrinsic to extrinsic motivation, hence affecting engagement in general. This dual-framework approach enables a comprehensive analysis on how environmental factors, classroom design in this case, may influence teacher and student engagement and motivation. It allows for a better understanding of the coping mechanisms teachers develop to counterbalance the lack of resources and support associated with policy changes, pointing to the importance of having teachers involved in the design of learning environments. The study’s framework serves as a foundation for formulating recommendations on policy adjustments and developing classroom design practices that promote both student engagement and effective teaching.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness or the rigor of a study pertains to the level of confidence one can place in the data, interpretation, and methods employed to ensure the study’s quality (Polit Beck, 2014). In this research, I will establish the necessary protocols and procedures to warrant the study’s credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Credibility represents the foremost criterion in establishing trustworthiness. It holds particular significance because it demands that the researcher establish a clear connection between the research findings and the real-world context, thus demonstrating the accuracy of the research’s outcomes (Statistics Solu-

tions, 2020). Dependability concerns the consistency and reliability of research findings and the extent to which research procedures are meticulously documented, enabling external parties to follow, review, and evaluate the research process (Sandelowski, 1986; Polit et al., 2006; Streubert, 2007). Confirmability involves assessing the extent to which other researchers can confirm the research study’s findings. It focuses on ensuring that the data and interpretations are not mere products of the researcher’s imagination but are firmly grounded in the data collected (Korstjens Moser, 2018). Transferability refers to the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be applied or extended to other

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

contexts or settings. Within the realm of qualitative research, transferability primarily rests on the shoulders of those attempting to generalize findings. The qualitative researcher can enhance transferability by providing comprehensive descriptions of the research context and the underlying assumptions. It is then the responsibility of the individual seeking to apply the results to another context to determine the appropriateness of such a transfer (Trochim, 2020).

3. Results and Discussion

This section of the study presents the findings of the research questions. The public elementary school teacher-participants presented their experiences on the impact of classroom design on student engagement. Corollary to this, an investigation of their coping mechanisms with the educational management insights covering their experiences are discussed in this same section. The findings of the thematic analysis are presented along with the discussions based on the identified themes.

3.1. *Experiences on the Impact of Classroom Design on Student Engagement* —

3.1.1. *Hampered Creativity*—One of the emerging themes that occurred in the thematic analysis was the hampered creativity experienced by the teacher participants. DepEd teachers have been used to structuring the classroom in accordance to DepEd Educational Facilities Manual (2010). However, with DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2023 ordering the schools to clear school grounds, classrooms and all its walls of unnecessary artwork, decorations, tarpaulin and posters, teachers at the helm of innovation are tested on the ground. P3 was completely alarmed that the creativity skills of the teachers will be affected thereby affecting classroom engagement. On the other hand, P10 argued that the bare-walls classroom directive of DepEd will halt teachers to a certain level of effort only setting aside the institution of a positive learning environment. Teachers and other stakeholders, who often dress up their classrooms with numerous posters and instructional materials weeks before schools open — most of which come from their own pockets — were confused by the directive on classroom structuring (Chi, 2023). These results were consistent with a study conducted by Ford (2010), which hypothesized that it is critical to assess learning environments in light of the evolving pedagogies that educators are urged to use with the students of this generation. According to Uline et al. (2011), there is data that suggests the physical layout of schools may have an impact on teachers' decisions to work or not work in particular schools. Additionally, teachers must ascertain what is effective for both themselves and their students. Therefore, it is believed that giving teachers the flexibility to bring out their creativity through classroom design will enable them to make the classroom environment engaging.

3.1.2. *Lack of consideration to learners' diversity*—The recognition that learners are diverse and thus has alternating needs is a challenge covered in the bare-walls policy. These results corroborate the findings of the study of Chaney (2020) which showed a strong relationship between children's positive behaviors and the presence of decoration in the learning environment. There is more evidence to support the idea that teachers as classroom designers should take into account the profile of the learners. The results are further supported in the pa-

pers by Grube (2014) and Cheryan et al. (2014), which emphasize that although it may require time, money, and resources to create a warm, welcoming atmosphere in the classroom, some decoration changes such as painting the walls a color other than white or hanging up posters that are supportive of all genders and nationalities have been found to improve the learning

3.1.3. Restricted engagement—A well-designed classroom can create an environment that encourages active involvement, collaboration, and interaction among students. Teachers who are the end implementers of the novel classroom design policy are challenged to conform on the rule citing it as extreme and restrictive thereby limiting learner engagement in the classroom. P9 remarked that the policy can be demotivating for others who have long established decorating their classrooms from their own pockets. On the other hand, P2 reflected that engagement is affected as the classroom becomes uninviting. Lastly, P5 posited that decorations still enhanced the learning environment. These findings are found in the study conducted by Barrett et al. (2012), which investigated the verifiable impact of classroom

environment. All of the above-mentioned positive points, however, were refuted by Fisher (2014), who said that because students in actual classrooms are exposed to the same visual environment every day, they may become accustomed to it. For students that require different adjustments for learning inputs, this could be harmful.

design on students' rates of learning in elementary school. Design parameters were taken into consideration as contributing factors to entire learner participation, in addition to the standard principles of light, sound, temperature, air quality, choice, flexibility, connection, complexity, color, and texture. Furthermore, according to Ryan and Deci's Causality Orientations Theory (2000) which examined motives in individuals and distinguished between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation, classroom design can have an impact on students' causality orientations, which in turn has an impact on their engagement. Attractive furnishings, comfortable seats, and engaging materials can all contribute to the creation of a design that encourages intrinsic motivation and makes learning enjoyable in and of itself.

3.2. Coping Mechanisms—

3.2.1. Creating a warm classroom atmosphere—A theme that occurred in the content analysis showed that teachers attempted to build an engaging classroom atmosphere to compensate for the lack of visual materials that can help set the tone of the classroom into a conducive learning area. Creating such kind of atmosphere may include the use of engaging activities. P2 created such an atmosphere in the classroom by making sure that the entire area is well-lit. The answers of the participants suggest that

improving the physical conditions of the classroom where learners would feel comfortable during the learning process could potentially increase the likelihood of students feeling positive and engaged. Moreover, this aligns with the response of P4 where s/he mentioned that engaging students in class discussions and group activities help them be actively involved. Incorporating hands-on activities could also make the learning process more interactive and lively, according to the response of P7.

3.2.2. Use of supplementary materials—

Fig. 3. Experiences of DepEd teachers with the Impact of Classroom Design on Student Engagement

One of the emerging themes that occurred from the analysis is the use of supplementary materials. This may include the utilization of portable teaching aids and digital platforms to properly meet the needs and demands of the teaching and learning process. P5 emphasized that investing in portable teaching aids is convenient because you can easily attach or remove them when needed. This allows complying to the policy in providing a stimulating learning environment easier. Meanwhile, P8 used digital platforms in order to share resources and materials to learners, allowing visual aid to supplement information without having to clutter classroom walls. The findings of Ahmed (2018) revealed that the use of teaching aid help motivate students to be positive as they find the necessity of using them beneficial in enhancing students' English language performance. Thus, teachers should note that disregarding the use of these supplementary materials could be detrimental to students' motivation.

3.2.3. Learner Involvement—Another emerging theme that occurred was learner involvement where student autonomy is encouraged in the classroom. The content analysis of the study showed that P2 involved students in the process of redesigning the classroom. This helped learners understand the changes and become better engaged in their learning environment. Meanwhile, P9 attempted to encourage students to take on more responsibilities in their own learning, including setting their own learning goals, self-assessing their improvements, and asking for help when need be. The learning involvement process includes metacognition which requires students to think about their own learning and assess their progress. Lai (2011) defined metacognition simply as “thinking about thinking” consisting of two components: knowledge and regulation. Metacognitive knowledge encompasses knowledge about one’s learning capacity and the factors that might affect learning performance including learners’ knowledge about learning strategies and knowledge of when and why to use these strategies. In this regard, learner autonomy could only be present if students have metacognitive abilities of self-assessing their own progress and know when and where to situate themselves in the learning process.

3.3. Insights —

3.3.1. Classroom design creates a positive classroom culture—One of the themes that emerged in the content analysis is classroom design’s influence on classroom culture. P1 mentioned that a positive learning environment promote students to actively participate in class activities. Active class engagement is an indicator of a positive classroom culture where students feel free to be themselves and share ideas with others. This is in line with the answer of P6 where s/he suggested that communication, respect, and cooperation among students are keys to building a positive classroom culture.

3.3.2. Communication—One of the themes that emerged from the interviews is the importance of communication in implementing significant changes in the classroom.

3.3.3. Teacher involvement in the decision-making process—

Fig. 4. Coping mechanisms used by teachers to counter challenges involving classroom design and student engagement

Another theme that emerged from the findings of the study is the significance of involving teachers in coming up with policies that affect the classroom. Although a teacher’s main work is to facilitate the teaching and learning process through effective implementation of pedagogical and specialized knowledge, the global trend in educational reforms that structured many classrooms worldwide, particularly in the United States of America show that teachers nowadays possess new empowered roles in schools. Ideally, shared decision making which involve educators should be practiced in the school-level. However, challenges still arise involving this. More so, the practice may encounter difficulties when applied on higher levels of “centralized” decisions often imple-

mented nationwide (Lin, 2014). According to P4, school administrators should involve teachers in the process of decision-making, particularly when implementing new policies. Doing so could potentially help students and teachers in the teaching and learning process. However, the study of Gemechu (2014) revealed that this is not well-supported. In fact, school leaders viewed teacher involvement as ineffective, creating a gap in the ideal practice and its implementation. The lack of trust between school heads and teachers, absence of a democratic school leadership, no financial incentives, as well as lack of support and training were viewed as some of the factors that have impeded the involvement of teachers in the school decision-making process.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this part of the paper, the summary, findings, implications and future directions are drawn. The study aimed to explore the challenges, coping mechanisms, and management insights drawn

Fig. 5. Insights gained from the experiences

from the experiences of teachers on the impact of classroom design on student engagement. The participants were public school elementary teachers from the Schools Division of Davao City, Region XI. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the qualitative phenomenological research design was used. Thematic analysis was also utilized to analyze the themes of the study. Following the recommendations provided by Cresswell (2006), open-ended interview questions were used to gain a genuine insight of participants' experiences. With this interview technique, I allowed my participants to freely and honestly share how they understood the issue under investigation that is the impact of classroom design on student engagement.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis, the following themes were discovered. The challenges experienced by teachers on classroom design vis-à-vis learner engagement covered hampered creativity, lack of consideration to learners' diversity, and restricted engagement. The results showed that DepEd teachers were accustomed to setting up their classrooms in compliance with existing rules. They did, however, find it difficult to follow the new mandate, which required the schools to remove all extraneous artwork, decorations, tarps, and posters from every wall. However, the bare walls policy also failed to address the issue of acknowledging that students are varied and have fluctuating needs. Teachers continued to feel that students who easily understood pictures would benefit from having visuals all around them in the classroom. It has been discovered also that certain design modifications, such as painting the walls a color other than white or putting up posters that promote people of different genders and ethnicities, enhance the learning environment. Teachers, who are ultimately responsible for implementing the innovative classroom design policy, are also faced with challenges in adhering to it. They argue that the rule is very stringent and could potentially hinder student participation within the classroom. Meanwhile, the results of the research demonstrated that teachers employ the following coping strategies to address issues with classroom design on learner engagement: create a warm classroom atmosphere, use of supplementary materials, and learner engagement. In an effort to make up for the lack of visual aids that can assist establish the mood of the classroom into a conducive learning environment, teachers tried to create an interesting classroom environment. Engaging activities could be used to create this kind of mood. To appropriately address the needs and demands of the teaching and learning process, teachers also made use of digital platforms and portable teaching aids. In order to help students comprehend the modifications and improve their engagement with their learning environment, teachers also contended that students need to be involved in the decisions made regarding classroom design. Further, the educational management insights drawn from the study were: creating a positive classroom culture, communication, and teacher involvement in the decision-making process. As a result, engaged students are a sign of a supportive learning environment where they are encouraged to express their uniqueness and collaborate with one another. Teachers also mentioned that communication was critical to this kind of development. They believe that raising issues and making policy recommendations can result in adjustments that will help both educators and students. Finally, the teachers believed that it was crucial to take them into account while putting new reforms into place. They promoted the idea of implementing shared decision-making of fresh policies at the school level.

4.2. *Implications*—The results of the analysis revealed the following significant findings: The challenges faced by teachers regarding classroom design and learner engagement, particularly in response to directives like the bare-walls policy, underscore a tension between traditional teaching practices and evolving educational approaches. While such policies may aim to standardize and declutter learning spaces, they risk neglecting the diverse needs of both teachers and students. Teachers' resistance to the bare-walls policy reflects their belief in the importance of visual aids for learner comprehension and engagement. By removing familiar decorations, teachers perceive a loss of tools that facilitate learning, particularly for students who benefit from visual stimuli. This highlights the need for flexibility in policy implementation to accommodate different teaching styles and student learning preferences. Moreover, teachers' coping mechanisms reveal their resilience and adaptability in navigating restrictive policies. By creating a warm classroom atmosphere and utilizing supplementary materials, teachers strive to maintain an engaging learning environment despite limitations imposed by design directives. Incorporating student input into classroom design decisions not only fosters a sense of ownership but also enhances student engagement by aligning the learning space with their preferences and needs. From an educational management perspective, fostering a positive classroom culture, open communication, and teacher involvement in decision-making processes are crucial for successful policy implementation. Active class engagement serves as an indicator of a supportive learning environment where students feel empowered to participate and express themselves. Effective communication channels enable teachers to voice concerns and contribute to policy refinement, ultimately promoting collaboration and mutual understanding between stakeholders. In summary, tackling the problems of learner engagement and classroom design calls for a well-rounded strategy that embraces innovation while also recognizing the value of tradition. Learning environments that effectively support various teaching and learning needs can be created by educational institutions through the value of teacher knowledge, incorporation of student opinions, and collaborative decision-making.

4.3. *Future Directions*—The following future directions were surmised based on the findings of the study: The Department of Education may propose changes to support more accommodating regulations that enable customized classroom layouts according to the requirements of both educators and learners. Rather of imposing strict standards like the bare-walls requirement, the government might support recommendations that offer a foundation while letting teachers customize their classrooms. The DepEd may also spend funding on teacher support and training, which is crucial for giving educators the abilities and information they need to adapt to changing pedagogical trends in classroom design and student engagement. Lawmakers may examine current regulations on the layout and design of classrooms. It is time for the government to make improvements to the infrastructure and design of classrooms in order to improve the teaching and learning conditions for both teachers and students. Educational leaders and teachers may prioritize student input in the design and organization of learning spaces ensuring that classrooms resonate with learners and enhance engagement. To further create dynamic and inclusive learning environments that meet the changing demands of today's learners, they may embrace technological integration, promote collaborative decision-making, and support research and innovation. Researchers in the future may work on the same study with a different group of subjects and demographics. For improved results, additional methods that have not been employed in this study could also be investigated or implemented.

5. References

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